

Does Board Gender Diversity Influence Dividend Pay-Out? Evidence from Nigeria Non-Financial Services Sector

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Abstract: Board gender diversity also known as female directors and corporate dividend payout have been interrogated in the literature in developed and developing economies. However, there are no clarity in the identification of the problem and efforts to proffer solutions have been little focus. In this paper, effort is made to analyse the influence of board gender diversity on dividend payout using data from Nigeria non-financial services sector. The data was hand-picked and analysed using descriptive statistics and multiple random effects panel model regression. This paper illustrates that the female CEO and duality negatively influence the dividend ratio. The chairwomen use dividend to appease the shareholders. Moreover, Boards of Directors with at least a woman reduce the dividend payout. The findings are consistent with agency theory, as female boards increase payouts to reduce agency conflict between boards and shareholders. Regulators and stakeholders stand to benefit from the study as more empirical evidence on the role of women in corporate world is provided. The findings are limited to stakeholders in non-financial services sector since there are variations in different sectors. The study is also limited due to the period covered and therefore, the validity of its findings is restricted to the years covered. Also, the choice of methods used may be subject of debate since different methods produce different results. Finally, broader set of variables may be used in future research effort linking female directors with dividend payout.

Keywords: Board Characteristics, Board Gender Diversity, Board of Directors, CEO, Dividend payout, Female CEO.

1. Introduction

Over time, countless board gender diversity studies have focused on the effects of having a female CEO or female board member on firm performance (Ahern & Dittmar, 2012; Dezső & Ross, 2012; Matsa & Miller, 2013; Yahaya, 2022), as well as CEO characteristics (Yahaya, 2022). Furthermore, recent research has suggested that female executives can have a strong influence on governance. Shaukat et al. (2016) argue that female directors concentrate on corporate social responsibility. Miller and Triana (2009) find that female executives also invest more in research and development programs. Faccio et al. (2016) note that female executives take fewer debts and make less risky financial decisions.

There is also evidence that female leaders tend to exert a more positive impact on the workplace environment than do their male colleagues (Carter et al., 2003; Adams & Ferreira, 2009). Also, the quality of conference discussion on complex situations is also enhanced as a result of the presence of female directors. The bond between female director and the dividend has been intensively examined in the finance industry. Chen et al. (2017) examined data from 1,691 companies in the USA over 1997 and 2001, and the results showed that dividend increases with the number of female executives. Ye et al. (2019) use linear regression models for data from 8,876 companies in 22 countries between

2000-2013 to conclude that a significant rapport exists between gender diversity and higher dividend. Al-Rahahleh (2017) examines the influence of board members with gender diversity on the company's dividend policy using data from financial companies in Jordan over 2009-2015. The results suggest that higher gender diversity would have a positive effect on dividend policy. Gyapong et al. (2019) obtained consistent findings when they apply the fixed-effects model to analyze data from 326 non-financial companies listed on the Australian Securities Exchange for 2009-2014. In striking contrast, Saeed and Sameer (2017) point out that having an additional female board member would lead to lower dividend in three developing markets: India, China, and Russia, based on data from 552 countries over 2007-2014.

Moreover, they provide mixed findings on the influence of gender diversity on dividend pay-out. A report from the Boston Consulting Group in 2017 indicates a worrisome scenario on the number of female directors on the board of directors. This necessitated the need to examine the impact of female directors on dividend policy in Nigeria. As Nigeria has not yet fully transformed into a market economy, government role in the economy is apparent. This paper uses data from 75 companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group for 2012-2021. The findings from the paper emphasizes how the growing gender diversity on the BOD could affect the dividend policy of listed companies in Nigeria.

2. Literature Review

Al-Amarneh et al. (2017) examine the effect of gender diversity on the dividend policy of 13 listed companies in the Amman Stock Exchange over 2005-2014. The research showed that BOD with gender diversity pays higher cash dividends because female directors could settle investor requirements better. However, the BOD tends to become more conservative during a financial crisis, so they will retain capital and reduce dividends because female executives have a strategy of taking less risk. Adams and Ferreira (2009) suggest that female CEOs attend conferences more frequently and were more diligent than male CEOs. Eckel and Füllbrunn (2015) recommend that women are more cautious than their male counterparts, so their decisions are

less radical and do not show overconfidence. Companies with more female CEOs have lower financial leverage ratios because female executives tend to engage in lower debts and also select less risky investment decisions and portfolios (Faccio et al. 2016). Arshad et al. (2013) and Obradovich and Gill (2013) and Yahaya (2022) suggest that CEO duality had a significant impact on dividend policy, but they do not show how CEO gender might play a role in dividend decisions. Román-Martínez et al. (2012) claim that female CEOs could use their managing ability to cooperate with managers for personal benefits, in which case dividends are reduced. Chen et al. (2017) study the role of gender in BOD on the dividend policy of companies listed on the US Stock Exchange over 1997-2001. The findings show that companies with female CEOs had a higher dividend payouts, as they tended to dividends as a monitoring tool in companies with weak corporate governance. The research emphasized the influence of individual female CEOs on dividend. Ye et al. (2019) evaluated the correlation between gender diversity in BOD and dividends. The findings suggest that BOD with gender diversity use dividends to reduce agency costs. Specifically, both the number and ratio of female members in BOD affect dividend policies.

According to Chen et al. (2017), Yahaya (2022), and Ye et al. (2019), BOD with higher gender diversity pay higher dividends. Moreover, Li and Srinivasan (2011), Wintoki et al. (2012) also argue that BOD with both male and female directors would improve business administration and better protect the interests of shareholders which, in turn, would encourage higher dividend payout. Al-Amarneh et al. (2017) argue that BOD with gender diversity would pay lower dividend. Furthermore, Román-Martínez et al. (2012) observe that the number of female CEOs have a negative influence on company dividend decisions. As the relationship between board gender diversity and dividend payout is mixed, we suggest that:

H₁: Board gender diversity in the BOD does influence dividend pay-out.

Gender diversity may affect the efficiency of the board of management at both the personal and group levels. At the individual level, it is understood that women and men are

different in how they can improve the efficiency of the BOD. For example, Adams and Ferreira (2009) observe that female CEOs are more diligent and joined conferences more frequently than did their male counterparts. According to Bernardi and Arnold (1997), male executives tend to pay greater attention to their incomes and career promotion opportunities, and were more likely to bypass regulations to achieve success, while female leaders preferred to follow laws and principles. Gul et al. (2011) recognize that female directors are more sensitive to moral and ethical issues. Moreover, women have a lower risk preference than do males (Charness & Gneezy, 2012). From these observations, we propose a second hypothesis:

H₂: There are no differences between males and females in dividend decisions.

3. Methodology

We collected the data from the Nigerian Exchange Group and mitigate extreme values and outliers in the sample as they can lead to biased estimates and inferences. The final data sample includes 750 observations from 75 companies over 2009-2017. We used the Panel Data method in the empirical analysis for the Panel Data model presents data with detailed information with specific complications that are sufficient for empirical research. In view of this advantage, the Panel Data model is widely used in research and scientific analysis.

For the dependent variable, we follow Chen et al. (2017) and choose the Dividend Payout Ratio, which is the ratio of the total amount of dividends paid to shareholders relative to the net income of the company (DPO). Explanatory variables in the analysis include gender diversity in the Board of Directors (BOD). We measure gender diversity based on the definitions given in Chen et al. (2017) and Ye et al. (2019). According to Leary and Michaely (2011) and Harford et al. (2008), Financial Leverage (LEV) affect company revenues; Growth reflects fluctuations in the company value, so growth influences dividends of the company. Ye et al. (2019), Leary and Michaely (2011), and Harford et al. (2008) also observe that liquidity is another indicator of dividend. Based on the previous studies, we choose the control variables, as shown

in Table 2.

In order to explore the influence of board gender diversity on dividend, we consider the following Model:

$$DPO_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 FCEO_{i,t} + \beta_2 FCHAIR_{i,t} + \beta_3 FCEODUAL_{i,t} + \beta_4 FD_{i,t} + \beta_5 LEV_{i,t} + \beta_6 LIQ_{i,t} + \beta_7 GRTH_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Whereas:

DPO = Dividend Pay-out, measured as dividend/equity shares (Al-Amarneh et al., 2017; Yahaya, 2017; Yahaya, 2022).

FCEO = Female CEO, 1 if company's CEO is female, 0 else, in year t (Eckel & Füllbrunn, 2015; Yahaya, 2022)

FCHAIR = Female Chair, 1 if BOD has a chairwoman, 0 else, in year t (Arshad et al., 2013; Obradovich & Gill, 2013).

FCEOD = Female duality, 1 if /Chair/CEO is female, 0 else, in year t (Arshad et al., 2013; Obradovich & Gill, 2013).

FD = Female director, 1 if company has at least 1 female director on the board, 0 else, in year t (Yahaya, 2022).

LEV = Leverage, measured as total liabilities/total assets (Harford et al., 2008; Leary & Michaely, 2011; Yahaya & Awen, 2020; Yahaya & Andow, 2015; Yahaya, 2022)

LIQ = Liquidity, measured as total cash/total assets (Harford et al., 2008; Leary & Michaely, 2011).

GRWTH = Growth, measured as EPS this year/EPS last year (Harford et al., 2008; Leary & Michaely, 2011).

α = Constant

β_{1-7} = Coefficients

i = Firm script ($i = 75$)

t = Year script ($t = 10$)

ε = Error term

In the model, we add Leverage (LEV) or financial leverage, the ratio of total debt to total assets (Harford et al. 2008; Leary & Michaely, 2011; Yahaya & Andow, 2015). Previous studies have shown that companies with high leverage paid fewer dividends (Jensen et al., 1992). The results show that companies with higher leverage face higher financing costs, so they have to retain cash to meet debt obligations. Furthermore, these companies would be monitored closely by their creditors. Consequently, excessive financial leverage has negative influence on company profits, so that dividends will also be affected. We also add liquidity (Leary & Michaely, 2011; Harford et al., 2008). Liquidity (LIQ) reflects business conservatism and company financial

strengths. An increase in LIQ leads to improvements in business performance in order to affect the pay-out decision. Furthermore, the study follows Leary and Michaely (2011) and Harford et al. (2008) to add the growth rate of EPS. Earnings per share is calculated as company profit divided by the equity shares. EPS directly affects share price, so that a high EPS shows more robust business performance, with dividends tend to increase.

Hwang et al. (2013) uses Panel Data and the Hausman specification test in estimating and testing the model specifications to examine the influence of financial leverage on dividend policy. Okoye et al. (2016) reexamine dividend policy, and uses the methods as used in Hwang et al. (2013). With samples presented in the Panel data, we use the Hausman test to select either the fixed effects model (FEM) or the random effects model (REM).

4. Findings and Discussion

The findings are presented in Tables 1 to 3 as follows:

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Obs	Mean	Std. D.	Min	Max
FCEO	750	.078	.269	0	1
FCHAIR	750	.117	.322	0	1
FCEOD	750	.034	.181	0	1
FD	750	.545	.498	0	1
LEV	750	.502	.222	.044	.914
LIQ	750	.045	.048	.001	.258
GRWTH	750	-.040	3.785	-23.758	19.615

Source: From STATA 14

As indicated in Table 1, the number of observations is 750 (75 firms, 10 years). The female chief executive officer (FCEO) averages 7.8% with a standard deviation of 26.9% and least and highest mean of 0% and 100%. Similarly, female chairwoman (FCHAIR) averages 11.7% with a standard deviation of 32.2% and least and highest mean of 0% and 100%. Female CEO duality (FCEOD) averages 3.4%

with a standard deviation of 18.1% and least and highest mean of 0% and 100%. Also, female director (FD) averages 54.5% with a standard deviation of 49.8% and least and highest mean of 0% and 100%. on the control variables, leverage (LEV) averages 50.2% with a standard deviation of 22.2% and least and highest mean of 4.4% and 91.4%. Liquidity (LIQ) averages 4.5% with a standard deviation of 4.8% and least and highest mean of 0.1% and 25.8%. Finally, firm growth (GRWTH) averages -4% with a standard deviation of 3.785% and least and highest mean of -23.758% and 19.615%. Table 2 presents the findings of the regression diagnostics before the final regression.

Table 2

Regression Diagnostics

Test	Chi ²	P-Value
Hetttest	4.597	.000
Mean VIF	1.46	
Hausman	14.67509	.2597
R ²	54.446%	

Source: From STATA 14

From the findings in Table 2, two observations are clear: there is heteroskedasticity in the residual and the appropriate panel model is REM. Table 3, therefore takes of these two results as follows:

Table 3

Final REM Results

Variable	Coefficients	t-value	p-value
FCEO	-.0023***	-11.602	.000
FCHAIR	.0104***	16.868	.000
FCEOD	-.0093***	-13.168	.000
FD	-.0040***	-22.844	.000
LEV	-.0538***	-43.574	.000
LIQ	-.1195***	-43.505	.000
GRWTH	-.0015***	-19.722	.000
Constant	.053***	37.049	.000

Source: From STATA

There is substantial variation among the values of some of the variables. GRWTH have high variation, whereas the other variables do not have such substantial changes over time.

FCEO, FCHAIR, FCEODUAL, and FD are all dummy variables, having a maximum value of 1 and a minimum value of 0. FCEO, FCHAIR, and FCEODUAL have very low mean values of 0.078, 0.117, 0.034, and 0.075, respectively. These numbers show that, for companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group, less than 12% had female executives holding important roles, such as CEO or chair of the board, or both. FD has a mean value of 0.545, which indicates that just over one-half of the companies in the sample have at least one female director as a member of the board. LEV has a maximum value of 0.914, a minimum value of 0.044, and a mean value of 0.502, which means that, on average, one naira in assets is used to invest 0.502 naira in debt. GRWTH has a maximum value of 19.615, a minimum value of -23.758, and a mean value of 3.785, which indicates that the average growth rate of earnings per share is 378.5%. LIQ has a maximum value of 0.258, a minimum value of 0.001, and a mean value of 0.045, which suggests that for each naira in asset, the company has 0.045 naira in cash.

Multicollinearity arises in the data set when there are close linear dependencies among the independent explanatory variables. In short, it is a potential problem with the data, and not with the model specification. In Table 2, the VIF is presented matrix to check the collinearity among the independent variables. Kim (2019) suggests arbitrarily that, when the VIF is less than 3.3, there is no potential collinearity issue. Table 2 shows that there are no case of multicollinearity in the data set. Therefore, it seems that the variable selection is appropriate and should not affect the empirical results, namely the estimates and their statistical significance. Also, consider the Variance Inflation Factor again; according to Hair et al. (1998), if the VIF factor is higher than 10, that means the model has severe collinearity. In management sciences research, it seems that when VIF is greater than 2, the model is deemed to have high collinearity. As there is a large number of quantitative explanatory variables in the models, the quantitative variables will use a VIF value of 2, and qualitative variables will use a VIF value of 10. Table 2 shows that the VIF is less than ten, which means there is no severe

collinearity among the variables in the alternative model specifications.

Furthermore, in order to choose between the FEM (Fixed Effects) and REM (Random Effects) models, the study performs the Hausman specification test to choose between them, namely: Table 2 indicates that the p-value is 0.2597, which is greater than 0.05, so we do not reject the null hypothesis, so that the REM model will be used in this case in the empirical analysis. Also, after performing the Breusch-Pagan test for heteroskedasticity in the residuals of the estimated model, the result in Table 2 show that heteroskedasticity is present. Heteroskedasticity is a correctable flaw in the model which can affect the validity of the empirical results.

After resolving the presence of heteroskedasticity in the model, the article shows the results in Table 3. It indicates that 54.446% of the range of the dependent variable DPO (dividend payout ratio) is accounted for by the independent explanatory variables in the model. The FCEO and FCEODUAL variables are critical findings in the empirical outcomes. Table 3 shows that the two variables are inversely related to the dividend payout ratio. If the CEO is female, the dividend payout ratio decreases by 13.3%; if a female CEO takes the duality position, the dividend payout ratio decreases by a smaller amount of 3.6%. Women tend to take less risk than men, so they are less likely to raise external capital. Consequently, they are more likely to retain profits for reinvestment and development, so the payout ratio is reduced accordingly. The empirical findings are consistent with the results in Lyness and Thompson (1997), and Faccio et al. (2016). Table 3 also shows the positive relationship between dividend payout and the FCHAIR variable. Specifically, companies with chairwomen increase the dividend payout ratio by 15.1%. This finding is consistent with those in Arshad et al. (2013), Obradovich and Gill (2013), who suggest that chairwomen tend to take less risk than their male counterparts, retain a higher proportion of profits, and use dividend payments as an administrative method. Román-Martínez et al. (2012) suggest that female board members tend to use their authority for personal benefits, cooperate more closely with

managers, and reduce dividend payments.

GRWTH is inversely proportional to DPO. When EPS increases by 1%, the dividend payout ratio decreases by 1.5%. This empirical outcome is not consistent with those in Nizar Al- Malkawi (2007), and Farooq et al. (2009), who suggest that EPS could have a positive effect on company dividend ratios. However, an alternative explanation is that the EPS growth rate and dividend ratio do not have a stable relationship with each other, as the EPS growth rate is affected by multiple factors, such as the change in the number of shares outstanding and the earnings growth rate. When a company decides to issue additional shares, EPS will decrease accordingly. There is a positive relationship between financial leverage and the payout ratio. When a company increases leverage by an additional 1%, the dividend payout ratio increases by 16.5%. The empirical findings in the paper are consistent with those in DeAngelo et al. (2006) and Yahaya and Andow (2015). The purpose of using leverage is to enhance profits, which can accelerate earnings if a company uses leverage appropriately. However, Rozeff (1982), Jensen et al. (1992), and Ye et al. (2019) observed that companies with high leverage tended to pay fewer dividends since these companies need to retain their earnings to pay debts on time. Furthermore, indebted companies will be monitored tightly by creditors, so these firms may not pay a high dividend as do less levered firms. The liquidity (cash ratio) is inversely proportional to the dividend payout ratio. When the cash ratio increases by 1%, the dividend ratio decreases by 158%. This empirical outcome is consistent with agency theory in DeAngelo et al. (2006), Amidu and Abor (2006), and Ye et al. (2019). This outcome suggests that a firm will pay higher dividends to prevent managers from over-investing and wasting resources, so that it will lead to reductions in the cash ratio.

In order to test the sustainability of the model, the author robust the dependent variable DPO, and the results are presented in Table 3. The empirical results presented in Table

3 show that all the variables have a statistical significance of 1% when the author test sustainability using the robust DPO. FD do not have statistical significance when the author consider the effects on DPO, but it has statistical significance when effect is tested with DPO robust.

The paper examined the effects of non-financial and financial factors on the dividend payout ratio of listed companies on the Nigerian Exchange Group. The analysis focused on gender diversity. Previous studies about this topic in Nigeria are scarce and generally unavailable, so the present research findings provide factual evidence and practical suggestions for public policy in Nigeria. The empirical results show that the female CEO and CEO chairwoman decrease the dividend ratio, while chairwomen tend to use the dividend ratio as a tool in managing companies effectively. Moreover, it was found that BODs with least a female members tended to decrease the dividend payout ratio. Following Setia-Atmaja et al. (2009) and Ben-Nasr (2015), the study supports the theory.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

In conclusion, the study suggests that gender diversity in BODs influence the dividend payout ratio. The findings can be used to enhance the decisions of investors who want to consider profits through cash dividend payments. The results can be used as a basis for enhancing corporate governance for listed non-financial services firms in Nigeria through public regulatory policy, and more widely for countries at similar stages of economic and financial development.

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